

Received: 30th March 2019

Revised: 13th May 2019

Accepted: 20th June 2019

Transient analysis of steel leaf spring using Finite Element Method

Naran.B.Vasava,
Lecturer in Mechanical Engineering,
Shri K.J.Polytechnic,Bharuch.
vasavanaran@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The leaf spring used in automobile light passenger vehicle is analyzed using ANSYS software. The finite element result showing stresses and deflection verified with existing analytical solutions. In the present work steel leaf spring is modeled in solid works 2009 and finally analysis is carried out using ANSYS to predict the von-misses stresses and maximum deflection under the static and transient dynamic condition.

Keywords—leaf spring, finite element Method, Static analysis, transient analysis, stress and Deflection.

I.INTRODUCTION

Leaf springs are crucial suspension used on light passenger vehicles necessary to minimize the vertical vibrations impacts and bumps due to road irregularities and to create the comfort ride. Leaf springs are widely used for automobile and railroad suspensions. The leaf spring should absorb the vertical vibrations and impacts due to road irregularities by means of vibrations in the spring deflection so that the potential energy is stored in spring as strain energy and released slowly so increasing the energy storing capabilities of a leaf spring and ensure a more compliant suspension system. The amount of elastic energy that can be stored by a leaf spring volume unit [6] is given by Eq. (1).

$$S=1/2 * \sigma^2/E \quad (1)$$

Where σ is the maximum allowable stress induced into the spring and E is the modulus of elasticity, both in the longitudinal direction. Considering that the dominant loading on leaf spring is vertical force. Three-dimensional finite element analysis of the leaf spring consists of a computer model or design that is stressed and analysed for specific results.

The leaf spring is analysed for static and transient dynamic condition for its strength and deflection using 3-D finite element analysis. The general-purpose finite element software ANSYS is used for present study. The variation of bending stress and deflection values are predicted in static condition while optimization of leaf spring for the optimization of Leaf Spring, Accurate prediction of stresses and deflection is necessary for that reason we must perform modal and transient analysis of Leaf Spring..

II.DESIGN CALCULATION OF STEEL LEAF SPRING

Material of Leaf Spring: - 50Cr1V23,

Composition of material is 0.45%C, 0.1-0.3% Si, 0.6-0.9%Mn and 0.9-1.2%Cr.

Basic Requirement:-

Max. Weight capacity of vehicle : - 2690 Kg.

The total weight is distributed into two halves front and rear.

Front axle weight (FAW):-1090kg

Rear axle weight (RAW):-1600kg

Force Motors Trax Cruiser is equipped with 2 nos. of Semi Elliptical Leaf Spring at the rear side:-

Load acting on the Leaf Spring Assembly: - 1600/2

Transient analysis of steel leaf spring using Finite Element Method

: 800 x9.81

:7848.00N

Calculation of the Leaf Spring:-Consider the Leaf Spring is Cantilever Beam. So the Load acting on the each assembly of the Leaf Spring is acted on the two ends of the Leaf Spring. Load acted on the Leaf Spring is divided by the two because of consideration of the Cantilever Beam.

2 x W: - 7848 N

W: - 7848/2

W:-3924N

By considering, factor of safety for the safety purpose of the Leaf Spring 2.5 for automobile leaf spring. So the allowable stress for the Leaf Spring is as under:-

Tensile Strength (σ_t) :- 2000 / 2.5
:- 800 N/mm²

Yield Strength (σ_y) :- 1800 / 2.5
:- 720 N/mm²

Bending stress generated in the Leaf Spring are as under:-

$$\sigma_b := (6x W x L) / (n x b x t^2)$$
$$\sigma_b := 668.53 \text{ N/mm}^2$$

So, the stress generated in the Leaf Spring is lower than the Allowable Design Stress. So Design is safe.

Deflection generated in the Assembly of Leaf Spring are as under :-

$$y := (12 x W x L^3) / E x b x t^3 ((2 x n_g) + (3 x n_f))$$
$$y := (12 x 3924 x 575^3) / 2.1x10^5 x 60 x 7.5^3 ((2x4)+(3x2))$$
$$y := 126.30\text{mm}$$

III. MODELLING OF STEEL LEAF SPRING.

Modeling of Leaf Spring is performed in Solid works 2009.

Create below sketch with the help of Leaf Spring length and Camber. Divide Leaf Spring length and camber into equal division and draw a spline which passes through intersection of Camber and length division which shows as under.

Fig.1 Leaf spring create by divisional method of generation

Fig.2 Solid model of leaf spring

IV.STATIC ANALYSIS OF STEEL LEAF SPRING

- 1) After Creating Solid Model of Steel Leaf Spring in SOLIDWORKS 2009. Save that model in *.IGES format.
- 2) Import above 3D Model in ANSYS Workbench Static Structural Module for Static FEM Analysis.
- 3) Create Leaf Spring Material 50Cr1V23
- 4) Define Contact between leaves of Leaf Spring.

Contact Type:- No Separation

- 5) Create meshing of Leaf Spring.

Type of Meshing: - 3D

Type of Elements:- Brick

Number of Nodes: - 3517

Number of Elements: - 403

- 6) Apply Boundary Condition

Define Fixed Support at outer surface of small leaf.

- 7) Define force of 3924 N at two end of spring.
- 8) Results of Analysis.

Fig.3 Maximum Stresses Contour

Transient analysis of steel leaf spring using Finite Element Method

Fig.4 Maximum Deflection Contour

V. TRANSIENT DYNAMIC ANALYSIS

After analyzing static analysis of leaf spring, using same boundary condition the 300mm deep road is consider for transient response of leaf spring

Apply Transient Force

Fig.5 transient force applied for a step load.

Here, considering 300mm deep road with time step taken is 0-0.1 sec.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Total load} &= mgh + \text{vehicle weight} \\ &= 5101.2 \text{ N} \quad \text{where, } h=300\text{mm} \end{aligned}$$

Tabular Data					
	Steps	Time [s]	X [N]	Y [N]	Z [N]
1	1	0.	0.	0.	0.
2	1	0.1	0.	5101.2	0.
3	1	1.	0.	0.	0.
*					

Fig.6 Graphical representation of transient force response

Fig.7 Maximum overtime stresses

Parameters	Analytical Results	Static Analysis Results	% Variation
Von-Misses Stresses(MPa)	668.53	695.46	3.87
Maximum Deflection(mm)	126.30	124.8	3.61

Result Table:

Conclusion:

Above results show that Static FE Analysis matches with the Analytical results. This reflects the practical behavior of spring in actual condition.

For the optimization of Leaf Spring, Accurate prediction of stresses and deflection is necessary for that reason we must perform modal and transient analysis of Leaf Spring. The response of leaf spring under transient condition and the stresses of maximum over time is within the limit.

REFERENCES:

[1]Rajendra,I.,Vijayarangan,S.Optimum“Design of a composite leaf spring using Genetic algorithms,Int.Jr.of computer and structures 79 2001:pp.1121-1129.

[2]Rajendra,I.,Vijayarangan,S.”Optimum design and analysis of composite leaf spring” journal of institute of engineers India 82 2002:pp180-187.

[3]Senthil Kumar and vijayarangan,”Analytical and experimental studies on fatigue life prediction of steel leaf spring and composite leaf spring using life data analysis”ISSN 1392 1320 material science Vil.13 No.2 2007.

[4] SAE, 1980. Manual on Design and Application of Leaf Springs, SAE HS 788. Society of Automotive Engineers, Warrendale, PA.

[5]Ansys 12.1 for FEA Analysis

[6] Machine design by Dr.sadhu singh, Khanna publishers, edition 2004.

[7] ASM Hand Book, Volume 21 Composites.

[8] NPTEL Composite material by Prof.P.C.Pandey, Dept.of Civil Eng., IISc Bangalore.